

A Proof of the existence of the constant L in Proposition 2

Lemma 4. *Let $X \sim \mathcal{N}(m, C)$, and let*

$$Y = f(X) = X^\top AX, \quad (66)$$

where $A \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ is symmetric positive definite. Let

$$\mu_{(2)} := \mathbb{E}[(Y - \mathbb{E}[Y])^2], \quad \mu_{(4)} := \mathbb{E}[(Y - \mathbb{E}[Y])^4]. \quad (67)$$

If $\mu_{(2)} > 0$, then

$$\mu_{(4)} \leq 15\mu_{(2)}^2. \quad (68)$$

Proof. By Theorem 3.3.2 in [13], the fourth cumulant of Y is

$$c_4(Y) = 48 \left(\text{Tr}((AC)^4) + 4m^\top (AC)^3 Am \right). \quad (69)$$

Since $\mu_{(4)} = 3\mu_{(2)}^2 + c_4(Y)$, it suffices to control $c_4(Y)/\mu_{(2)}^2$.

Let

$$M := \sqrt{A}m, \quad \Sigma := \sqrt{AC}\sqrt{A}. \quad (70)$$

Because AC and Σ are similar, we may rewrite

$$\mu_{(2)} = 2 \text{Tr}(\Sigma^2) + 4M^\top \Sigma M, \quad (71)$$

$$c_4(Y) = 48 \left(\text{Tr}(\Sigma^4) + 4M^\top \Sigma^3 M \right). \quad (72)$$

Set

$$S := \text{Tr}(\Sigma^2), \quad T := M^\top \Sigma M. \quad (73)$$

Since Σ is symmetric positive semidefinite,

$$\text{Tr}(\Sigma^4) \leq (\text{Tr}(\Sigma^2))^2 = S^2, \quad (74)$$

and

$$M^\top \Sigma^3 M = (\sqrt{\Sigma}M)^\top \Sigma^2 (\sqrt{\Sigma}M) \quad (75a)$$

$$\leq \lambda_{\max}(\Sigma^2) M^\top \Sigma M \quad (75b)$$

$$\leq \text{Tr}(\Sigma^2) M^\top \Sigma M = ST. \quad (75c)$$

Therefore,

$$c_4(Y) \leq 48(S^2 + 4ST). \quad (76)$$

Moreover,

$$\mu_{(2)} = 2S + 4T. \quad (77)$$

If $S = 0$, then $\Sigma = O$, hence $T = 0$, and therefore $\mu_{(2)} = 0$, contradicting the assumption. Thus $S > 0$, and with $x := T/S \geq 0$,

$$\frac{c_4(Y)}{\mu_{(2)}^2} \leq 48 \frac{S^2 + 4ST}{(2S + 4T)^2} = 12 \frac{1 + 4x}{(1 + 2x)^2}. \quad (78)$$

Now define

$$\phi(x) := \frac{1 + 4x}{(1 + 2x)^2}, \quad x \geq 0. \quad (79)$$

Then

$$\phi'(x) = -\frac{8x}{(1 + 2x)^3} \leq 0, \quad (80)$$

so ϕ is decreasing on $[0, \infty)$. Hence

$$\phi(x) \leq \phi(0) = 1, \quad (81)$$

which gives

$$\frac{c_4(Y)}{\mu_{(2)}^2} \leq 12. \quad (82)$$

Consequently,

$$\frac{\mu_{(4)}}{\mu_{(2)}^2} = 3 + \frac{c_4(Y)}{\mu_{(2)}^2} \leq 3 + 12 = 15. \quad (83)$$

This completes the proof. \square

B Complete proof of Lemma 2

Proof. We divide the proof into four steps.

1. Linearization of the truncation region.

First, we show that, under the assumption, the truncation region $\{f(x) \leq \kappa_t^q\}$ is asymptotically approximated, in the standardized coordinates, by a half-space determined by the linear term. Let $X_t \sim \mathcal{N}(m_t, C_t)$, and decompose it as

$$X_t = m_t + \sqrt{C_t} Z_t, \quad Z_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I). \quad (84)$$

Substituting this decomposition into f , we obtain the representation

$$f(X_t) = m_t^\top A m_t + 2v_t^\top Z_t + Z_t^\top B_t Z_t, \quad (85)$$

where $B_t := \sqrt{C_t}A\sqrt{C_t}$. Hence, the truncation condition $f(x) \leq \kappa_t^q$ can be rewritten as

$$f(X_t) \leq \kappa_t^q \iff \frac{1}{\|v_t\|} v_t^\top Z_t + \frac{Z_t^\top B_t Z_t}{2\|v_t\|} \leq \frac{\kappa_t^q - m_t^\top A m_t}{2\|v_t\|}. \quad (86)$$

Let

$$M_t := \sqrt{A}m_t, \quad \Sigma_t := \sqrt{A}C_t\sqrt{A}. \quad (87)$$

Then, by Lemma 1 and the assumption of this lemma,

$$\|M_t\|^2 = m_t^\top A m_t \rightarrow V' > 0. \quad (88)$$

Hence, for sufficiently large t , there exists a constant $c_0 > 0$ such that

$$\|M_t\| \geq c_0. \quad (89)$$

Moreover, $B_t = \sqrt{C_t}A\sqrt{C_t}$ is similar to AC_t , and $\Sigma_t = \sqrt{A}C_t\sqrt{A}$ has the same eigenvalues as AC_t . Therefore, we have

$$\|B_t\| = \lambda_{\max}(\Sigma_t), \quad \text{Cond}(\Sigma_t) = \text{Cond}(AC_t) \leq R. \quad (90)$$

Now,

$$\|v_t\|^2 = m_t^\top AC_t A m_t = M_t^\top \Sigma_t M_t \geq \lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_t) \|M_t\|^2. \quad (91)$$

Since $\text{Cond}(\Sigma_t) \leq R$, we have

$$\lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_t) \geq \frac{\lambda_{\max}(\Sigma_t)}{R}. \quad (92)$$

Hence

$$\|v_t\|^2 \geq \frac{c_0^2}{R} \lambda_{\max}(\Sigma_t) = \frac{c_0^2}{R} \|B_t\|. \quad (93)$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\|B_t\|}{\|v_t\|} \leq \frac{\sqrt{R}}{c_0} \sqrt{\|B_t\|}. \quad (94)$$

By Proposition 2, since $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} AC_t = O$, we have

$$\|B_t\| = \lambda_{\max}(\Sigma_t) \rightarrow 0. \quad (95)$$

It follows that

$$\frac{\|B_t\|}{\|v_t\|} \rightarrow 0. \quad (96)$$

Hence the quadratic term

$$\frac{Z_t^\top B_t Z_t}{2\|v_t\|} \quad (97)$$

is negligible compared with the linear term on the $Z_t = O_p(1)$ scale. Indeed, we have

$$\left| \frac{Z_t^\top B_t Z_t}{2\|v_t\|} \right| \leq \frac{\|B_t\|}{2\|v_t\|} \|Z_t\|^2. \quad (98)$$

Since $\|B_t\|/\|v_t\| \rightarrow 0$ and $\|Z_t\|^2 = O_p(1)$, it follows that

$$\frac{Z_t^\top B_t Z_t}{2\|v_t\|} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{in probability.} \quad (99)$$

Define

$$e_t := \frac{v_t}{\|v_t\|}, \quad \alpha_t := \frac{\kappa_t^q - m_t^\top A m_t}{2\|v_t\|}. \quad (100)$$

Then

$$f(X_t) \leq \kappa_t^q \iff e_t^\top Z_t + \frac{Z_t^\top B_t Z_t}{2\|v_t\|} \leq \alpha_t. \quad (101)$$

Hence, in standardized coordinates, the truncation region is asymptotically approximated by the half-space

$$e_t^\top z \leq \alpha_t. \quad (102)$$

2. Determination of the asymptotic half-space.

Second, we show that the truncation region is asymptotically equivalent to the half-space determined by the q -quantile of the standard normal distribution. Let

$$Y_t := e_t^\top Z_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1), \quad R_t := \frac{Z_t^\top B_t Z_t}{2\|v_t\|}. \quad (103)$$

Then the truncation event can be written as

$$S_t := \{Y_t + R_t \leq \alpha_t\}. \quad (104)$$

Since κ_t^q is the q -quantile of $f(X_t)$, we have

$$q = \Pr(S_t) = \Pr(Y_t + R_t \leq \alpha_t). \quad (105)$$

For any fixed $\varepsilon > 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \{Y_t \leq \alpha_t - \varepsilon\} \cap \{|R_t| \leq \varepsilon\} \\ & \subset \{Y_t + R_t \leq \alpha_t\} \subset \{Y_t \leq \alpha_t + \varepsilon\} \cup \{|R_t| > \varepsilon\}. \end{aligned} \quad (106)$$

Therefore,

$$\Pr(Y_t \leq \alpha_t - \varepsilon) - \Pr(|R_t| > \varepsilon) \leq q \leq \Pr(Y_t \leq \alpha_t + \varepsilon) + \Pr(|R_t| > \varepsilon). \quad (107)$$

Since $Y_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, it follows that

$$\Phi(\alpha_t - \varepsilon) - \Pr(|R_t| > \varepsilon) \leq q \leq \Phi(\alpha_t + \varepsilon) + \Pr(|R_t| > \varepsilon). \quad (108)$$

Moreover, by Step 1, $R_t \rightarrow 0$ in probability, so for every fixed $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$\Pr(|R_t| > \varepsilon) \rightarrow 0. \quad (109)$$

Hence,

$$\Phi(\alpha_t - \varepsilon) - o(1) \leq q \leq \Phi(\alpha_t + \varepsilon) + o(1). \quad (110)$$

Therefore,

$$\alpha_t \rightarrow \Phi^{-1}(q) =: \alpha_q. \quad (111)$$

Finally, note that

$$\{\mathbb{I}\{S_t\} \neq \mathbb{I}\{Y_t \leq \alpha_q\}\} \subset \{|Y_t - \alpha_q| \leq |R_t| + |\alpha_t - \alpha_q|\}. \quad (112)$$

Hence, for any fixed $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \Pr(\mathbb{I}\{S_t\} \neq \mathbb{I}\{Y_t \leq \alpha_q\}) \\ & \leq \Pr(|Y_t - \alpha_q| \leq \varepsilon) + \Pr(|R_t| + |\alpha_t - \alpha_q| > \varepsilon). \end{aligned} \quad (113)$$

Since $Y_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ has a continuous density, while $R_t \rightarrow 0$ in probability and $\alpha_t \rightarrow \alpha_q$, the right-hand side converges to 0. Therefore,

$$\Pr(\mathbb{I}\{S_t\} \neq \mathbb{I}\{Y_t \leq \alpha_q\}) \rightarrow 0. \quad (114)$$

Thus the truncation region is asymptotically equivalent to the half-space

$$e_t^\top z \leq \alpha_q. \quad (115)$$

3. Truncated first and second moments.

Third, we calculate the first and second truncated moments by replacing the truncation event with its asymptotic half-space. Define

$$\psi_t := \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{S_t\} Z_t \right], \quad \Psi_t := \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{S_t\} Z_t Z_t^\top \right], \quad (116)$$

and let

$$H_t := \{Y_t \leq \alpha_q\}. \quad (117)$$

By Step 2, we have $\Pr(\mathbb{I}\{S_t\} \neq \mathbb{I}\{H_t\}) \rightarrow 0$. We first consider the truncated first moment. Since

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{S_t\} Z_t \right] - \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{H_t\} Z_t \right] = \frac{1}{q} \mathbb{E} [(\mathbb{I}\{S_t\} - \mathbb{I}\{H_t\}) Z_t], \quad (118)$$

the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{S_t\} Z_t \right] - \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{H_t\} Z_t \right] \right\| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{q} \mathbb{E} [\mathbb{I}\{\mathbb{I}\{S_t\} \neq \mathbb{I}\{H_t\}\} \|Z_t\|] \end{aligned} \quad (119a)$$

$$\leq \frac{1}{q} (\mathbb{E}[\|Z_t\|^2])^{1/2} \Pr(\mathbb{I}\{S_t\} \neq \mathbb{I}\{H_t\})^{1/2}. \quad (119b)$$

Since $Z_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$, we have $\mathbb{E}[\|Z_t\|^2] < \infty$, and therefore

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{S_t\} Z_t \right] = \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{H_t\} Z_t \right] + o(1). \quad (120)$$

Similarly, for the truncated second moment,

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{S_t\} Z_t Z_t^\top \right] - \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{H_t\} Z_t Z_t^\top \right] = \frac{1}{q} \mathbb{E} [(\mathbb{I}\{S_t\} - \mathbb{I}\{H_t\}) Z_t Z_t^\top]. \quad (121)$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{S_t\} Z_t Z_t^\top \right] - \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{H_t\} Z_t Z_t^\top \right] \right\|_F \\ & \leq \frac{1}{q} \mathbb{E} [\mathbb{I}\{\mathbb{I}\{S_t\} \neq \mathbb{I}\{H_t\}\} \|Z_t Z_t^\top\|_F] \end{aligned} \quad (122a)$$

$$\leq \frac{1}{q} (\mathbb{E}[\|Z_t Z_t^\top\|_F^2])^{1/2} \Pr(\mathbb{I}\{S_t\} \neq \mathbb{I}\{H_t\})^{1/2}. \quad (122b)$$

Since $\|Z_t Z_t^\top\|_F = \|Z_t\|^2$ and $Z_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$, we have $\mathbb{E}[\|Z_t\|^4] < \infty$. Hence,

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{S_t\} Z_t Z_t^\top \right] = \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{H_t\} Z_t Z_t^\top \right] + o(1). \quad (123)$$

To compute the truncated moments under the asymptotic half-space, define

$$U_t := (I - e_t e_t^\top) Z_t, \quad (124)$$

so that

$$Z_t = Y_t e_t + U_t, \quad Y_t = e_t^\top Z_t. \quad (125)$$

Since e_t is a deterministic unit vector and $Z_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$, both Y_t and U_t are linear transformations of the Gaussian vector Z_t . Hence (Y_t, U_t) is jointly Gaussian.

Moreover, we have

$$\mathbb{E}[U_t] = (I - e_t e_t^\top) \mathbb{E}[Z_t] = 0, \quad (126)$$

$$\text{Cov}(U_t) = (I - e_t e_t^\top) \text{Cov}(Z_t) (I - e_t e_t^\top)^\top = (I - e_t e_t^\top)^2 = I - e_t e_t^\top. \quad (127)$$

Finally, the cross-covariance between Y_t and U_t is

$$\text{Cov}(Y_t, U_t) = \mathbb{E}[Y_t U_t^\top] \quad (128a)$$

$$= \mathbb{E}[e_t^\top Z_t Z_t^\top (I - e_t e_t^\top)] \quad (128b)$$

$$= e_t^\top \mathbb{E}[Z_t Z_t^\top] (I - e_t e_t^\top) \quad (128c)$$

$$= e_t^\top (I - e_t e_t^\top) = 0. \quad (128d)$$

Since (Y_t, U_t) is jointly Gaussian and uncorrelated, Y_t and U_t are independent.

Therefore,

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{H_t\} Z_t\right] = \frac{1}{q} \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}\{Y_t \leq \alpha_q\} (Y_t e_t + U_t)] \quad (129a)$$

$$= \frac{1}{q} \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}\{Y_t \leq \alpha_q\} Y_t] e_t + \frac{1}{q} \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}\{Y_t \leq \alpha_q\} U_t]. \quad (129b)$$

By independence of Y_t and U_t , and since $\mathbb{E}[U_t] = 0$,

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}\{Y_t \leq \alpha_q\} U_t] = \Pr(Y_t \leq \alpha_q) \mathbb{E}[U_t] = 0. \quad (130)$$

Hence, by using the standard truncated normal identity

$$\mathbb{E}[Y_t | Y_t \leq \alpha_q] = -\frac{\phi(\alpha_q)}{\Phi(\alpha_q)}, \quad (131)$$

we obtain

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{H_t\} Z_t\right] = \mathbb{E}[Y_t | Y_t \leq \alpha_q] e_t = -\frac{\phi(\alpha_q)}{\Phi(\alpha_q)} e_t = -\lambda_q e_t, \quad (132)$$

where $\lambda_q := \phi(\alpha_q)/\Phi(\alpha_q) = \phi(\alpha_q)/q$.

Next,

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{H_t\} Z_t Z_t^\top\right] = \frac{1}{q} \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}\{Y_t \leq \alpha_q\} (Y_t e_t + U_t) (Y_t e_t + U_t)^\top]. \quad (133)$$

Expanding the product gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{1}{q} \mathbb{I}\{H_t\} Z_t Z_t^\top\right] \\ &= \frac{1}{q} \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}\{Y_t \leq \alpha_q\} Y_t^2] e_t e_t^\top + \frac{1}{q} \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}\{Y_t \leq \alpha_q\} Y_t U_t] e_t^\top \end{aligned} \quad (134a)$$

$$+ \frac{1}{q} e_t \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}\{Y_t \leq \alpha_q\} Y_t U_t^\top] + \frac{1}{q} \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}\{Y_t \leq \alpha_q\} U_t U_t^\top]. \quad (134b)$$

Again by independence of Y_t and U_t , together with $\mathbb{E}[U_t] = 0$, the two cross terms vanish. Also,

$$\frac{1}{q}\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}\{Y_t \leq \alpha_q\}U_t U_t^\top] = \mathbb{E}[U_t U_t^\top] = I - e_t e_t^\top. \quad (135)$$

Therefore,

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\frac{1}{q}\mathbb{I}\{H_t\}Z_t Z_t^\top\right] = \mathbb{E}[Y_t^2 \mid Y_t \leq \alpha_q] e_t e_t^\top + (I - e_t e_t^\top). \quad (136)$$

Hence, by using the standard truncated normal identity

$$\mathbb{E}[Y_t^2 \mid Y_t \leq \alpha_q] = 1 - \frac{\alpha_q \phi(\alpha_q)}{\Phi(\alpha_q)}, \quad (137)$$

we obtain

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\frac{1}{q}\mathbb{I}\{H_t\}Z_t Z_t^\top\right] = \mathbb{E}[Y_t^2 \mid Y_t \leq \alpha_q] e_t e_t^\top + (I - e_t e_t^\top) \quad (138a)$$

$$= \left(1 - \frac{\alpha_q \phi(\alpha_q)}{\Phi(\alpha_q)}\right) e_t e_t^\top + (I - e_t e_t^\top) \quad (138b)$$

$$= (1 - \alpha_q \lambda_q) e_t e_t^\top + (I - e_t e_t^\top) \quad (138c)$$

$$= I - \alpha_q \lambda_q e_t e_t^\top. \quad (138d)$$

Consequently, we obtain

$$\psi_t = -\lambda_q e_t + o(1) \quad \text{and} \quad \Psi_t = I - \alpha_q \lambda_q e_t e_t^\top + o(1). \quad (139)$$

4. Expansion of m_{t+1} and C_{t+1} .

Finally, we combine the asymptotic expansions of the truncated first and second moments obtained in Step 3 with the IGO update formulas, and derive the claimed expansions.

Using the IGO update formulas, we have

$$m_t^* = \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{1}{q}\mathbb{I}\{S_t\}X_t\right] = m_t + \sqrt{C_t}\psi_t \quad (140)$$

$$C_t^* = \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{1}{q}\mathbb{I}\{S_t\}(X_t - m_t^*)(X_t - m_t^*)^\top\right] = \sqrt{C_t}(\Psi_t - \psi_t \psi_t^\top)\sqrt{C_t}. \quad (141)$$

By (139),

$$m_t^* - m_t = -\lambda_q \sqrt{C_t} e_t + o(\lambda_{\max}^{1/2}(C_t)), \quad (142)$$

where we used that $\sqrt{C_t}o(1) = o(\lambda_{\max}^{1/2}(C_t))$. Since

$$e_t = \frac{v_t}{\|v_t\|} \quad \text{and} \quad \sqrt{A}\sqrt{C_t}v_t = \sqrt{A}C_t A m_t = u_t, \quad (143)$$

we have

$$\sqrt{A}\sqrt{C_t}e_t = \frac{u_t}{\|v_t\|}. \quad (144)$$

Therefore,

$$\sqrt{A}(m_t^* - m_t) = -\lambda_q \frac{u_t}{\|v_t\|} + o(\lambda_{\max}^{1/2}(AC_t)). \quad (145)$$

Next, by (139),

$$\Psi_t - \psi_t\psi_t^\top = I - (\alpha_q\lambda_q + \lambda_q^2)e_te_t^\top + o(1), \quad (146)$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} & \sqrt{AC_t^*}\sqrt{A} \\ &= \sqrt{AC_t}\sqrt{A} - (\alpha_q\lambda_q + \lambda_q^2)\sqrt{A}\sqrt{C_t}e_te_t^\top\sqrt{C_t}\sqrt{A} + o(\lambda_{\max}(AC_t)). \end{aligned} \quad (147)$$

Again using $\sqrt{A}\sqrt{C_t}e_t = u_t/\|v_t\|$,

$$\sqrt{AC_t^*}\sqrt{A} = \sqrt{AC_t}\sqrt{A} - (\alpha_q\lambda_q + \lambda_q^2) \frac{u_t u_t^\top}{\|v_t\|^2} + o(\lambda_{\max}(AC_t)). \quad (148)$$

Moreover, since

$$\left\| \frac{u_t}{\|v_t\|} \right\| = \frac{\|\sqrt{AC_t}Am_t\|}{\|\sqrt{C_t}Am_t\|} \leq \|\sqrt{A}\sqrt{C_t}\| = \lambda_{\max}^{1/2}(AC_t), \quad (149)$$

we have

$$\sqrt{A}(m_t^* - m_t)(m_t^* - m_t)^\top\sqrt{A} = \lambda_q^2 \frac{u_t u_t^\top}{\|v_t\|^2} + o(\lambda_{\max}(AC_t)). \quad (150)$$

Therefore, substituting the above expansions into the IGO update (15) for the covariance matrix in the \sqrt{A} -transformed coordinates yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \sqrt{A}C_{t+1}\sqrt{A} \\ &= \sqrt{A}C_t\sqrt{A} - \tau(\alpha_q\lambda_q + \lambda_q^2) \frac{u_t u_t^\top}{\|v_t\|^2} + \tau(1 - \tau)\lambda_q^2 \frac{u_t u_t^\top}{\|v_t\|^2} + o(\lambda_{\max}(AC_t)) \end{aligned} \quad (151a)$$

$$= \sqrt{A}C_t\sqrt{A} - (\tau\alpha_q\lambda_q + \tau^2\lambda_q^2) \frac{u_t u_t^\top}{\|v_t\|^2} + o(\lambda_{\max}(AC_t)). \quad (151b)$$

This completes the proof. \square